

EFFECT OF BASTI AND SWEDAN IN THE MANAGEMENT OF AMAVAT W.S.R. TO RHEUMATOID ARTHRITIS– A CASE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

In the classical literature Madhavanidana, Madhavakara describes Amavata in detail. Based on clinical similarities, Amavata can be compared to contemporary Rheumatoid Arthritis. Rheumatoid arthritis is the most common chronic inflammatory disease. Ama is a causative factor for Amavata. Ama dosha interacts directly with Vata dosha in Amavata, causing joint inflammation, deformity, and immobility in the fingers, feet, and ankles, as well as stiffness throughout the body. Langhana, Swedana, Deepana, Tikta-katu rasa, Virechana, Basti, and other aspects of Amavata management are described in detail in Ayurveda. In this study A 53 year old female patient with complaints of Shoola, Shotha and Sthamba of the knee, wrist, ankle and metacarpophalangeal joints of both hands since a year, morning stiffness for 1 hour was reported in our hospital kayachikitsa department OPD. Considering the Lakshanas and the blood investigations, it was diagnosed as Amavata. and treatment was planned in which

Shaman, Shodhan (basti) & Bahya Chikitsa were included. The results was a significant improvement in the symptoms as well as in the level of RA Factor, ESR, CRP & she was able to perform her routine work without any difficulty. Hence it is concluded that the given therapy can be of great help in managing the cases of Amavat.

KEYWORDS: Amavata, Rheumatoid arthritis, Basti, swedana, Shaman chikitsa, Bahyachikitsa.

INTRODUCTION

Amavata is first described as a separate disease in Madhava Nidana, where it is mentioned that Mandagni plays an important role in the manifestation of the disease. Pratyatma Laksana include Gatrastabdhat, Sandhishula, Sandhishotha, Sparshasahyata associated with extra articular symptoms like Angamarda (body Pain), Aruchi (loss of taste), Thrishna (thirst), Alasya(lack of enthusiasm), Gourava(heaviness), Klama(tiredness without doing work), Apaka(indigestion) and jwara.^[1]

Amavata is a chronic illness induced by the production of ama (toxin) and vitiation of the Vata and Kaphasthana in the body. The Sleshma sthana are primarily the synovial joints.^[2] The vitiated Vata circulates the Ama through the Dhamanis and lives in the Sleshma sthana, causing sandhishotha, sandhishoola, and sanchari vedana in both small and large joints.^[3] Amavata is a disorder that is quite similar to rheumatoid arthritis, which is a very severe ailment. Rheumatoid arthritis is a systemic inflammatory disease that affects the synovial joints and has extra-articular symptoms.^[4] Joint discomfort, stiffness, tenderness, and restricted movements are the most common symptoms. The Concepts of treatment for Amavata have been described by Acharya Chakrapani.^[5] Some therapy procedures that are Useful in Amavata include Langhana, Swedana, Tikta-Katu rasa dravyas, Deepana dravyas, Virechana, and Anuvasana Basti. If the chikitsa is properly followed, Amavata can be controlled.

AIM AND OBJECTIVE

To study the effect of Basti and Swedan in the management of Amvata.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

This is a single case clinical study conducted at Radhakisan Toshniwal Ayurvedic Hospital, Akola. The patient was treated with specific regimen & progress was assessed. After proper Councelling, the line of treatment was explained & written informed consent was taken.

Case history

Study in which a 53-year-old female patient, who had apparently been normal one years back, Gradually she noticed shool,s hoth and stambh in the knee, wrist, ankle, metacarpophalangeal

joint with mild stiffness. After few days, pain got aggravated and found difficulty in the daily routine activity with severe stiffness. Patient had visited Kayachikitsa- Out Patient Department, for Ayurvedic management. Patient was thoroughly examined and detailed history was taken & admitted in Kayachikitsa female ward for management.

Chief Complaint

The onset of symptoms developed around one years back. The symptoms such Shoola, Shotha and Sthamba of the knee, wrist, ankle and metacarpophalangeal joints of both hands since a year and morning stiffness for 1 hour.

History of Past Illness: No h/o of hypertension, diabetes and any other illness.

Menstrual history: Menopause

Personal history

1. Ahara- Samishra (mixed diet)
2. Vihara-Diwaswapna (morning sleep habit)
3. Nidra- Disturbed due to pain
4. Mala pravritti: Samyaka (Satisfactory)
5. Mutra pravritti: Samyaka (Satisfactory)
6. Vyasana: Tea (2-3 times a day)

General Examination

1. Vitals: Pulse rate: 79/min
2. Blood pressure: 130/90 mm/hg
3. Respiratory rate: 16/min

Systemic examination

On examination, the patient is conscious, RS = NAD,
CVS= S1, S2 Normal

Musculoskeletal examination

Inspection

Swelling – present over metacarpophalangeal joints of both hand, both wrist joints, both knee joint left ankle joint

Redness – absent

Difficulty in flexion and extension of metacarpophalangeal, wrist and knee joints

Table no. 1 Table no.2**Sandhishoth (swelling) Sandhishool(severity of pain)**

No pain	0
Occasional pain of bearable nature	1
Difficultly in joint movement due to pain	2
Can not move the joint due to pain and restriction	3

No swelling	0
Swelling involving only 1 joint	1
Swelling involving 2-5 joints	2
Swelling involving more than 5 joints	3

Table no. 3: Table no.4**Sandhistabdhata(Stiffness) Sparshasahatva(Tenderness)**

No stiffness	0
Up to 1 hours	1
1 to 2 hours	2
>2 hours	3

No tenderness	0
Subjective experience of tenderness	1
Wincing of face on pressure	2
Wincing of face and withdrawal of affected parts on pressure	3

Lab. Investigation

Hb –12.1 gm%

ESR – 60 mm/1hr,

CRP – 11 mg/dl,

RA Factor – 170 IU/ml(positive)

DIAGNOSIS

Patient was diagnosed as case of Amavata (Rheumatoid arthritis).

TREATMENT PLAN**Shodhan chikitsa**

Patient was given sarvang swedana (Fomentation) with Dashmoola Kwatha prior to basti karma (medicated enema).

Basti Karma

1) Ingredients of **Matra basti** – Brihat Saindhavadi Taila.

Saindhava Lavana (Rock salt), Shreyasi (Scindapsus officinalis), Rasna (Pluchea Lanceolata), Shatapushpa (Anethum sowa), Yavani (Trachyspermum ammi), Maricha (Piper Nigrum), Shunti (Zingiber officinalis), Kusta (Saussurea lappa), Sauvarchala (Sochal salt), Vida (Vida salt), Ajamoda (Carum roxburghianum), Madhuka (Glycyrrhiza glabra), Jiraka (Cuminum cyminum), Pushpaka (Inula racemosa), Kana (Piper longum), Eranda Taila (Ricinus communis), Shatapushpa Ambu (Anethum sowa), Kanji (Fermented gruel), Mastu. In this, Bruhatsaindhavadi tail Basti dose of 60 ml was given in morning session (10 am to 11am), for 7 days. Patient was detained for 30 minutes in left lateral position for optimum effect of therapy.

2) Vaitaran Basti

Ingredients of Vaitaran Basti

- 1) Tamarind puree- 50 gm.
- 2) Jaggery- 100 gm
- 3) Rock salt- 10 gm.
- 4) Cows urine- 250 ml
- 5) Sesame oil- 40 ml

Shamana chiktisa

- 1) Sinhanad Guggulu - (250 mg) three times a day
- 2) Punarnava Guggulu – (250 mg) three times a day
- 3) Amapachak vati (250mg) three times a day
- 4) Shunthi, Guduchi, Haritaki(4gm each) Kwath- 20 ml two times a day with lukewarm water.

Bahyachikitsa

- 1) Shothhar lepa(L.A)
- 2) sand sadation.

Table No. 5: treatment schedule.

IPD from 30/5/2023 to 6/6/23

Procedure	Dose	Days
Sarvang swedan	-	7
Matra basti	60ml	7
Sinhanad guggul	tid	
Punarnava guggul	tid	
Amapachak vati	tid	

Shunthi, Guduchi, Haritaki kwath	bd	
Shothhar lepa	Morning+ Evening	
Valukapottali swed	Evening	

OPD level medicine from 7/6/23 to 29/11/23

Sinhanad guggul	Tid
Punarnava guggul	Tid
Amapachak vati	Tid
Shunthi, Guduchi, Haritaki kwath	Bd
Shothhar lepa	Morning+ Evening
Valukapottali swed	Evening

IPD from 30/11/23 to 6/11/23

Sarvang swedan	-	7days
Matra basti	60ml	7days
Sinhanad guggul	tid	
Punarnava guggul	tid	
Amapachak vati	tid	
Shunthi, Guduchi, Haritaki kwath	bd	
Shothhar lepa	Morning+ Evening	
Valukapottali swed	Evening	

OPD level medicine from 7/11/23 to 23/4/24

Sinhanad guggul	Tid
Punarnava guggul	Tid
Amapachak vati	Tid
Shunthi, Guduchi, Haritaki kwath	Bd
Shothhar lepa	Morning+Evening
Valukapottali swed	Evening

IPD from 24/4/24 to 4/5/24

Matra basti and vaitaran basti were given alternate day

Sarvang swedan		7 days
Matra basti	480ml	3 days
Vaitaran basti	60ml	4 days
Sinhanad guggul	1 tid	
Yograj guggul	1tid	
Punarnava mandur	1 tid	
Shunthi, Guduchi, Haritaki kwath	20ml bd	
Shothahar lepa	Morning+Evening	
Valukapottali swed	Evening	

OPD level Medicine 5/5/24 to 15/5/24

Sinhanad guggul	Tid
Yograj guggul	Tid
Punarnava mandur	Tid
Shunthi, Guduchi, Haritaki kwath	20ml bd
Shothahar lepa	Morning+Evening
Valukapottali swed	Evening

OBSERVATION AND RESULTS

During the course of the treatment, there was marked decrease in the severity of symptoms Like pain, swelling and morning stiffness and improvement in the appetite, generalized Weakness and range of motion of the affected joints. Hematological investigations which Were done at regular intervals also showed significant improvement which is shown in the Table below.

Assessment criteria

	BT 30/5/23	AT 6/6/23	BT 30/11/23	AT 6/11/23	BT 24/4/24	AT 4/5/24
Sandhishool	2	1	2	1	1	1
Sandhishoth	3	2	2	1	1	0
Sandhistabdhata	1	1	1	0	1	0
Sparshasahatva	2	1	1	0	1	0

Haematological investigation

The image displays three panels of laboratory reports from Ayurved Rugnalaya Central Pathology Laboratory. Each panel includes a header with the lab name and address, followed by patient information and a table of results.

Left Panel (Sample 1):

- HAEMOGRAM REPORT:** Hemoglobin: 9.6 gm% (F: 12.0-14.0, M: 13.0-17.0); Erythrocytes: 4.06 million/cumm (4.5-5.5); HCT: 29.8% (40-54); MCV: 73.4 fl (76-96); MCH: 23.6 pg (27-34); MCHC: 32.2 g/dl (31-36); Total Leucocyte Count: 9,300/cumm (4,000-10,000); Diff. Leucocyte Count: Neutrophils 64%, Lymphocytes 27%, Eosinophils 01%, Monocytes 08%, Basophils 00%; Platelet Count: 3,10,000/cumm (1,50,000-4,50,000); ESR: 40 mm (F: 00-20, M: 00-10).
- SEROLOGY REPORT:** C-Reactive Proteins (CRP): 13.21 mg/dl (Upto 6.0 mg/dl).
- S. Rheumatoid Factor (RA Test):** 33.21 IU/ml (Upto 20 IU/ml).

Middle Panel (Sample 2):

- HAEMOGRAM REPORT:** Hemoglobin: 11.3 gm% (F: 12.0-14.0, M: 13.0-17.0); Erythrocytes: 4.58 million/cumm (4.5-5.5); HCT: 32.6% (40-54); MCV: 71.0 fl (76-96); MCH: 24.7 pg (27-34); MCHC: 34.8 g/dl (31-36); Total Leucocyte Count: 9,700/cumm (4,000-10,000); Diff. Leucocyte Count: Neutrophils 67%, Lymphocytes 25%, Eosinophils 02%, Monocytes 06%, Basophils 00%; Platelet Count: 3,75,000/cumm (1,50,000-4,50,000); ESR: 38 mm (F: 00-20, M: 00-10).
- SEROLOGY REPORT:** C-Reactive Proteins (CRP): 8.3 mg/dl (Upto 6.0 mg/dl).
- S. Rheumatoid Factor (RA Test):** 4.2 IU/ml (Upto 20 IU/ml).

Right Panel (Sample 3):

- HAEMOGRAM REPORT:** Hemoglobin: 12.1 gm% (F: 12.0-14.0, M: 13.0-17.0); Erythrocytes: 4.52 million/cumm (4.5-5.5); HCT: 33.1% (40-54); MCV: 73.2 fl (76-96); MCH: 26.8 pg (27-34); MCHC: 36.6 g/dl (31-36); Total Leucocyte Count: 10,400/cumm (4,000-10,000); Diff. Leucocyte Count: Neutrophils 70%, Lymphocytes 24%, Eosinophils 01%, Monocytes 05%, Basophils 00%; Platelet Count: 3,56,000/cumm (1,50,000-4,50,000); ESR: 60 mm (F: 00-20, M: 00-10).
- BIOCHEMISTRY REPORT:** Blood Sugar, Random: 107 mg/dl (70-140).
- SEROLOGY REPORT:** C-Reactive Proteins (CRP): 11 mg/dl (Upto 6.0 mg/dl).
- S. Rheumatoid Factor (RA Test):** 170 IU/ml (Upto 20 IU/ml).

Date	Rheumatoid factor (IU/ml)	C-reactive protein(mg/dl)	ESR(mm/hour)	Haemoglobin (gm%)
20/5/2023	212	-	-	-
27/10/2023	170	11	60	12.1
28/3/2024	33.21	13.21	40	9.6
19/9/2024	4.2	8.3	35	11.3

DISCUSSION

The Chikitsa Siddhant for Amavata was first described by Chakradatta. Langhana, Swedana, medicines with Tikta, Katu Rasa, and Deepana action, Virechana, Snehapana, and Anuvasana, and Ksharabasti are all included. Amavata is regarded as a Rasaja Vikara and an Amashayotha vyadhi. In such cases, Langhana is the first line of defence. The ideal measure for the treatment of Ama has been stated in Yogaratnakar Langhana. Due to the existence of Ama, Ruksha sweda has been supported in the form of Valuka pottali in the Amavata. It helps to balance the vitiated Vata Dosha, which relieves pain and stiffness. The medications utilised in the therapy procedure aid in controlling the disease's pathogenesis. On the action of Basti, Vagabhatta says the Virya of Basti is conveyed to Apana and then to Samana Vata, which may regulate the function of Agni. It then goes to Udana, Vyana, and Prana, thus providing its efficacy all over the body.^[6]

Vaitarana Basti has been mentioned by Chakradutta in Niruhadhikar 73/32. the qualities of Vaitarana Basti can be considered as Laghu, Ruksha, Ushna, Tikshna. Majority of the drugs have Vata Kapha Shamaka action. Owing to these properties treatment with the Basti has provided significant improvement in sign and symptom of disease. The Tikshna Guna of Basti helps in overcoming the Srotodushti resulting due to Sanga, thus help in breaking down the pathogenesis of disease.

Simhanad Guggul- It has properties to reduce Swelling, stiffness, inflammation. It has purgative Action and balances all doshas.^[7] Compositions Of the Simhanada Guggulu were containing enzyme activating (Deepan), neutralizing bio toxin (Ama Pachan), reducing oedema (Shothaghna), analgesic(Vedanasthapaka), energy enhancing (Balya) and Antirheumatic (Amavatahara) etc. Actions which Helped to enhance the digestive & metabolic capacity And to mitigate the bio toxins as well as to prevent The bio toxins formation into the body, as a result Simhanada Guggulu helped to reduce the clinical Manifestations of Amavata (Rheumatoid arthritis) And also to break down the pathogenesis (Samprapti) Of Amavata.^[8]

Guduchi- It is bitter and astringent in taste, digestive, Relieves bio toxins (Ama), relieves Tridosha, diuretic In nature hence relieves swelling.^[9] Shunthi- It is pungent in taste, digestive in nature, relieves constipation and pain.^[9] Haritaki – It relieves the inflammation.^[9] Ampachan vati effectively alleviate this Ama dosha. It helps in restoring healthy digestion, absorption, assimilation and metabolism of food elements.

CONCLUSION

In the Sama stage of Amavata one should plan the treatment which pacifies the Vata and does pachana of the Ama in local and at systemic level considering the strength of the patient. Also early diagnosis and appropriate intervention is key to prevent deformities. Hence there is necessity of a systematic treatment protocol based on the principles of Ayurveda and thus a combination of treatment was planned which apart from giving symptomatic relief to the patient also helps in breaking the pathogenesis and efficiently tackle the disease. The present case study shows clinically significant improvement in patient's subjective and objective metrics post treatment indicating the decrease in severity of the disease. Thus justifying the efficacy of Basti & swedan treatment along with shamanoushadhi in the management of Amavata.

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